

~~Bibl.~~
85/1803r

Int. Rice Res. Newslett. 10(5):14
International Rice Research Institute
P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines

Effect of a conditioned medium on callus production and plant regeneration in rice anther culture

F.J. Zapata, L.B. Torrizo, and R.R. Aldemita, Tissue Culture Facility, IRRI

Although the efficiency of rice callus production is increasing, total efficiency still is low (no. of calli/no. pollen grains), considering that 1 rice anther has about 1,000 pollen grains. Tobacco and barley anthers produce more calli if the culture medium has been conditioned. We studied the effect of conditioned medium (CM) on rice callus production.

Conditioning medium (C) was prepared by culturing mature anthers (pollen grains with starch granules) of Giza 170 and Taipei 309 in Gamborg's

liquid B5 as a base medium. It contained 2% sucrose, 0.5% glucose, and 0.5 mg indoleacetic acid/litre, 0.5 mg benzyladenine/litre, and 1.0 mg 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid/litre as growth regulators at pH 5.6 (E₁₀). Plating density was 13 anthers/ml of medium. Anthers were incubated in the dark for 7 d, crushed, and the debris was separated from the medium by centrifugation at 100 × g for 5 min.

CM was prepared by diluting C with fresh medium at 1:0, 1:1, 1:2, 1:4, 1:8 (C:fresh E₁₀ medium). Fresh E₁₀ medium was the control.

Taipei 309 and Giza 107 anthers at mid-uninucleate to early binucleate development were plated at 5 anthers/ml in the CM treatments. They were incubated at 8 °C for 8 d and kept in

dim light conditions until calli formed. One-mm calli were inoculated in the regeneration medium. The base medium was semisolid Murashige and Skoog with 1 mg naphthalene acetic acid/litre and 1 mg kinetin/litre as growth regulators, and 0.8% agar at pH 5.6.

More Taipei 309 calli formed on all CM dilutions than in the control (see table). At 1:8 dilution, callus production was 1.6 times higher than in the control. On subsequent plant regeneration, the 1:2 dilution gave the highest percentage of callus-producing green plants. Perhaps CM triggered embryogenic calli production, thus increasing plant regeneration efficiency.

In contrast, CM reduced the efficiency of Giza 170 callus production and green plant regeneration (see table). \mathcal{J}

Effect of CM on callus production and green plant regeneration in Taipei 309 and Giza 170. IRRI, 1985.

Data	Medium ^a								
	Taipei 309				Giza 170				
	E ₁₀	1:8	1:4	1:2	E ₁₀	1:4	1:2	1:1	Pure CM
Anthers plated (no.)	415	372	367	316	316	288	298	54	22
Calli produced (no.)	729	1022	995	741	874	676	711	0	0
Callus production ^b (%)	175.7	274.8	271.1	234.5	276.6	234.7	238.6	0	0
Calli plated for regeneration (no.)	31	34	40	34	38	42	38	0	0
Callus-producing green plants (no.)	11	13	11	17	26	22	16	0	0
Callus-producing green plants ^c (%)	35.5	38.2	27.5	50.0	68.4	52.4	42.1	0	0
Green plant production (no.)	38	38	41	58	70	60	48	0	0
Average green plant production ^d (no.)	1.2	1.1	1.0	1.7	1.8	1.4	1.3	0	0

^aThe ratio means 1 part CM and 8, 4, 2, or 1 part fresh E₁₀ medium.

^bCallus production (%) = $\frac{\text{calli produced (no.)}}{\text{anthers plated (no.)}} \times 100$.

^cCallus-producing green plants (%) = $\frac{\text{callus-producing green plants (no.)}}{\text{calli plated for regeneration (no.)}} \times 100$.

^dAverage green plant production (no.) = $\frac{\text{green plant production (no.)}}{\text{calli plated for regeneration}}$